

Reaction Rates and Mechanisms in Aqueous-Organic Solvents : I-Water-Dioxane System

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A new correlation between reaction rate and mechanism and medium effects in aqueous-organic solvents was proposed. This correlation was derived quantitatively and was supported by the data shown for different reactions in water-dioxane mixtures. Such a correlation has the advantage that it does not involve any acidity function but does however need precise measurements of the water ionisation constant over the full aqueous-organic solvent composition range at the different temperatures. Mechanisms of acid- and base-catalysed reactions were discussed on the basis of solvation characteristics and activity coefficient behaviour of the particular reacting substrate and transition state in the reaction. A distinction between the different groups of these reactions was also reviewed and was applied for reactions in water-dioxane mixtures.

HAMMETT acidity function appears to be well established for aqueous solutions in both acidic as well as basic media. The original concept, providing the relevant ionisation occurred, a particular acidity function was independent of the class of indicator used to measure it, has been proved incorrect¹⁻⁴. This makes the use of acidity functions as a criterion of mechanism reliant upon knowledge of the variation of reaction rate with acidity function for reactions of known mechanism. In particular to assign a mechanism to a given reaction, a series of reactions conforming to the possible alternatives must previously have been studied. Less extensive studies and spectrophotometric measurements of acidity function have already been reported for solutions of mixed solvents. For a fixed concentration of hydrochloric acid over the full aqueous organic solvent (ethanol, acetone or dioxane) composition range there⁵⁻⁸ was a minimum acidity at a particular solvent composition. H_0 scales have also been recorded for $HClO_4$ ^{9,10} and HCl and H_2SO_4 ^{11,12} in 40-60 and 60-40 water-dioxane mixtures. Comparison of H_0 for H_2SO_4 in 5-95% dioxane-water¹³ with that for H_2SO_4 in water showed that the former was greater for acid concentration up to 6 mole/liter. The ionisation of various uncharged acids and bases in ethanol-and dioxane-water mixtures was investigated⁵ by a differential potentiometric method. An interesting comparison of acidity measures for ethanol-water mixtures with particular emphasis on the acidity functions H_0 and H_- was reported¹⁴. The basicity of aqueous alcohols or dioxane containing base has also been measured¹⁵. In all the aqueous alcohols studied a regular change in basicity was observed. This is quite unlike the previous data for H_0 ^{5,8}. Qualitatively the situation can be explained as a gradual and continuous change in the effective autoprotolysis constant and in the difference in energy of the proton relative to water.

Very few studies have been reported in which reaction rates are correlated with acidity function in aqueous-organic solvents. $\log k_1$ is approximately a linear function of H_0 for the HCl catalysed rearrangements of phenylpropenyl- and ethynylpropenyl carbinol⁶. The rates of the acid catalysed hydrolysis of methyl toluene-4-sulphinate in aqueous dioxane increased faster than acid but slower than H_0 with changing acid concentration or solvent composition¹⁶.

However, in aqueous-organic solvents, acidity function and its correlations with reaction rates and mechanisms have not been sufficiently studied, both experimentally and theoretically. The aim of the present investigation is to present a new correlation between reaction rates and medium effects in these media. This correlation will be derived quantitatively and tested for the different acid- and base-catalysed reactions. Mechanisms of these reactions will also be discussed on the basis of solvation phenomena. Experimental data in the literature^{8,16-20} supporting the conclusions will be presented.

Theoretical

What I wish to present, now, is a correlation of reaction rate and mechanism with medium effects for acid- and base-catalysed reactions in aqueous-organic solvents. This is based on my discovery that, for most such reactions^{8,16-20}, plots of $(\log k_{obs} - pK_w)$ versus $\log C_w$, at constant temperature, are generally very nicely linear. Examples are given in Fig.1. Equation (1) is therefore applicable in which C_w is the concentration and K_w is the ionisation constant of the water which is present as a component of the solvent system and k_{obs} is the observed rate constant.

$$\log k_{obs} - pK_w = n \log C_w + \text{constant} \quad (1)$$

The slope of any of these straight lines constitutes a parameter, called n , which describes the manner in which the particular reaction responds to acid or base catalysis. A value for n could be looked upon as the change in number of solvated water molecules in passing from reactants to the transition state in the rate determining step. This is an extreme interpretation.

By analogy with Bunnett's observations²¹ for acid solution it is probable that n is a function of both the mechanism of the reaction and the chemical structure of the reacting substrate. This probability cannot be assessed until many more experimental results are available for consideration. It is well known that the rates of acid- and base-catalysed reactions depend on the acid and base concentration. But they do not all depend in the same way. It is worth noting that studies with mixed solvents permit two rather different sorts of variation of acidity and as a result two rather different kinds of correlation of rate with medium effects. One type of variation is that obtained by changing the concentration of a strong acid (or base) in a solvent of fixed composition^{6, 22}. This type of variation minimises the change in the properties of the medium other than acidity. Consequently such solutions should be particularly favorable for investigating mechanistic implications of correlations of rate with acidity. Acidity function scales for changing acid concentration in a fixed solvent composition will then have similar significance and usefulness as the corresponding scales for aqueous solutions providing ion association is negligible. However, in some cases this is not true, particularly for solvents of low dielectric constant where ion association becomes significant.

Another type of variation of acidity for mixed solvents is that given by changes in the solvent for fixed concentration of acid (or base) solute^{7, 8, 17-19}. This kind of variation will usually involve large changes in the properties of the medium. As a result it should not be surprising that correlations between rate and H_0 are not exact and are in fact rather poor⁶, particularly for the solvents of lowest dielectric constant. Acidity functions for a fixed acid (or base) concentration in a series of aqueous solutions with varying solvent composition apparently have less generality and usefulness and therefore less significance. Correlations of reaction rates with acidity function scales are also not as satisfactory as for solutions in which the catalysing acid (or base) concentration is varied in a fixed solvent composition. Even so, these results are of considerable interest in view of the author's hypothesis which predicts linear correlation between $(\log k_{obs} - pK_w)$ and $\log C_w$ in aqueous-organic solvents. Very nice straight lines were obtained for water-dioxane mixtures^{8, 16-20} in both lower as well as higher dielectric constant media (Fig. 1).

On the other hand, it is evident²³ that the ionisation constant of water, K_w , varies with progressive

addition of organic solvents. Thus while $K_w = 1.008 \times 10^{-14}$ in pure water, it takes the value 23.99×10^{-16} , 18.09×10^{-17} and 13.95×10^{-19} in 20, 45 and 70% dioxane-mixtures by weight at 25°. This means that K_w should be considered as a function of solvent composition and is not constant as considered before^{1, 4, 24, 25}.

Fig. 1. Test of equation (I) for the different reactions
□ Ref 16, Δ Ref 17, × Ref 18, O Ref 19

Since the velocity constants and mechanisms are quite firmly established for the reactions under consideration^{8, 16-20} the observed proportionality between $(\log k_{obs} - pK_w)$ and $\log C_w$ lends strong support to the validity of the author's hypothesis. It should be noted that this new approach is applicable only to reactions in aqueous-organic solvents, and not to reactions in pure aqueous acidic or basic solutions. It is therefore of interest to evaluate what information on the mechanism can be obtained from this relationship in more general cases.

Medium Function and Reaction Rates and Mechanisms

Zucker and Hammett hypothesis²⁶ stated that reactions whose rate follows the appropriate indicator acidity function operate through a unimolecular conversion of the active species, while reactions whose rate tends to follow the stoichiometric acidity of the solution operate by a bimolecular reaction of the active species with solvent water. Thus the use of the Zucker-Hammett treatment as a criterion of mechanism is limited particularly when the dependence of rate with acidity falls somewhere between the two possibilities allowed by the theory.

Bunnett²¹ noted that for many reactions ($\log k_1 + H_0$) was a linear or approximately linear function of $\log a_w$ where w is the slope of the graph. Bunnett²¹ has suggested that the value of w for an acid-catalysed reaction may provide a useful criterion for the mechanism of that reaction. However, for certain reactions the plots appropriate to the determination of w were not linear. In these cases, one of other three equations is obeyed and enables the deduction of a parameter w^* which is a useful criterion of reaction mechanism. However it is unwise⁴ to take the Bunnett criteria, or generally the acidity function concept, alone as the only evidence for the mechanism of a particular reaction. Other independent confirmatory evidence is desirable.

The acidity function dependence of reaction rates will probably not only depend on the mechanism of the reaction and the solvation of the hydrogen or the hydroxide ion but also on the solvation characteristics and activity coefficient behaviour of the particular reacting substrate and transition state in the reaction.

I-Acid-catalysed reactions

The indicator acidity functions, treated originally as empirical concepts, have been rationalised by Bascombe and Bell^{27,28} who showed that the high acidities encountered in concentrated acid solutions are primarily due to the strong hydration of the proton in these solutions. The existence of protons in a tetrahydrated form ($H_9O_4^+$) has been suggested by many investigators using a variety of experimental techniques²⁹. When the solvation is taken into account, the relevant proton transfer equilibrium may be written as

where B is an electrically neutral weak base; p , q and r are the hydration numbers of B , H^+ and BH^+ respectively and $h = (p + q - r)$.

Gluecka³⁰ found that any anion larger than chloride ion may be considered as nonhydrated in the thermodynamic sense. As B and BH^+ are generally relatively large organic molecules, their solvation requirements may be neglected. However it is probably better to consider h in equation (2) as the difference in the solvation number.

Considering the solvation requirements, the main types of acid-catalysed reactions^{4,6} in aqueous-organic solvents may be summarised from the author's point of view as follows :

1—The A-1 mechanism for the hydrolysis of an organic solute S may be written as

The rate determining step is the unimolecular decomposition of the protonated hydrated substrate to an intermediate which rapidly reacts with water to give the reaction products. The rate of loss of the sum of the equilibrium concentrations of S and SH^+ is given by the equation

$$-\frac{d(C_S + C_{SH^+})}{dt} = k_1 C_{SH^+} \frac{f_{SH^+}}{f^*} \quad (3)$$

where k_1 is the rate constant for the slow step and f^* is the activity coefficient of the transition state for that step. The experimental (observed) first order rate constant k_{obs} is defined by the equation

$$k_{obs} = - \left[\frac{1}{C_S + C_{SH^+}} \right] \frac{d(C_S + C_{SH^+})}{dt} \quad (4)$$

combination of equations (3) and (4) with the expression for the acid ionisation constant K_{SH^+} of hydrated SH^+ leads to

$$k_{obs} = \left(- \frac{C_S}{C_S + C_{SH^+}} \right) \frac{k_1 C_H^+ f_H^+ f_S}{K_{SH^+} C_w^h f_w^h f_w^+} \quad (5)$$

In acid solutions the variation of the rate of an acid-catalysed reaction with changing solvent composition depends on the reaction mechanism and the relative values of the rate constants in each step of the mechanism. However the activity coefficient behaviour of the reactants and the transition state also makes a significant contribution to the variation of rate with solvent composition (medium effect). This activity coefficient behaviour is intimately connected with the solvation requirements of the reactants and transition state.

It was assumed²⁹ that the ratio of the activity coefficients is equal to unity. This might be justified in view of the theories of Stokes and Robinson^{31,32} and of Glueckauf^{29,30} concerning the thermodynamic behaviour of concentrated electrolytic solutions. Stokes and Robinson show that when hydration is taken into account, most of the deviation from ideality disappears, and the remaining deviations can be accounted for by the electrostatic interaction. The ion size parameter of KOH and NaOH is not very different from most other salts; consequently the electrostatic contribution to the activity coefficient ratio will be negligible²⁹.

However the author assumes that the activity coefficient ratio on the right-hand side of equation (5) varies with changes in the medium in essentially the same way as, K_w , the water ionisation constant. Such an assumption is a priori reasonable,

since K_w , is a function of solvent composition as mentioned above. Therefore, it may be assumed that this activity coefficient term in equation (5) would vary inversely with water ionisation constant according to equation (6) which leads to equation (7) for the observed rate constant (a_1 is a constant). This assumption may now be expressed as :

$$\frac{f_{H^+}}{f_w^h} \frac{f_s}{f^*} \propto \frac{1}{K_w} \text{ or } \frac{f_{H^+}}{f_w^h} \frac{f_s}{f^*} = \frac{a_1}{K_w} \quad (6)$$

and then,

$$k_{obs} = \left[\frac{C_s}{C_s + C_{SH^+}} \right] \frac{a_1 k_1}{K_{SH^+}} \frac{C_{H^+}}{C_w^h} \frac{1}{K_w} \quad (7)$$

Three situations now arise and depend upon the relative values of C_s and C_{SH^+} .

(a) If $C_{SH^+} \ll C_s$, the equilibrium (i) lies practically entirely on the left-hand side, equation (7) becomes

$$k_{obs} = \frac{a_1 k_1}{K_{SH^+}} \frac{C_{H^+}}{C_w^h} \frac{1}{K_w} \quad (8)$$

which on taking logarithms is equivalent to

$$\log k_{obs} - pK_w = \log C_{H^+} - h \log C_w + \text{constant} \quad (9)$$

It is clear that equation (9), for a fixed acid concentration, is a quantitative derivation of the empirical relationship expressed by equation (1). Therefore, it may be concluded that the activity coefficient ratio should be dependent on the reciprocal of the water ionisation constant as given by equation (6). Equation (9), or the empirical equation (1), has the advantage that it does not involve any acidity function but does however need precise measurements of the water ionisation constant, K_w , over the full aqueous organic solvent composition range at the different temperatures.

(b) If $C_s \simeq C_{SH^+}$ in the pre-equilibrium mixture, their concentrations are related via K_{SH^+} . Hence substitution for C_{SH^+} in equation (7) leads to

$$k_{obs} = \frac{a_1 k_1}{K_{SH^+}} \left[1 + \frac{a_1' C_{H^+}}{K_{SH^+} C_w^h K_w} \right]^{-1} \frac{C_{H^+}}{C_w^h} \frac{1}{K_w} \quad (10)$$

which, on rearrangement and taking the logarithms, gives

$$\log k_{obs} = \log (a_1 k_1) - \log \left[\frac{K_{SH^+} C_w^h K_w}{C_{H^+}} + a_1' \right] \quad (11)$$

(c) Finally if $C_s \ll C_{SH^+}$, then all the added substrate S is protonated in the pre-equilibrium step, equation (10) therefore reduces to

$$k_{obs} = \frac{a_1}{a_1'} k_1 \quad (12)$$

then the observed reaction rate will be independent of acid concentration.

2-The A-2 mechanism for acid-catalysed hydrolysis has a bimolecular rate determining step and may be represented by,

The rate of loss of the sum of the equilibrium concentrations of S and SH^+ is given by the equation

$$-\frac{d(C_s + C_{SH^+})}{dt} = k_2 C_{SH^+} C_Y \frac{f_{SH^+}}{f^*} \frac{f_Y}{f^*} \quad (13)$$

The experimental second order rate constant k_{obs} is defined by the equation,

$$k_{obs} = -\frac{1}{(C_s + C_{SH^+})(C_Y)} \frac{d(C_s + C_{SH^+})}{dt} \quad (14)$$

$$k_{obs} = \frac{C_s}{C_s + C_{SH^+}} \frac{k_2}{K_{SH^+}} \frac{C_{H^+}}{C_w^h} \frac{f_{H^+}}{f_w^h} \frac{f_s}{f^*} \frac{f_Y}{f^*} \quad (15)$$

Following the assumption expressed as equation (6) one may obtain,

$$\frac{f_{H^+}}{f_w^h} \frac{f_s}{f^*} \frac{f_Y}{f^*} = \frac{a_2}{K_w} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{and } k_{obs} = \left[\frac{C_s}{C_s + C_{SH^+}} \right] \frac{a_2 k_2}{K_{SH^+}} \frac{C_{H^+}}{C_w^h} \frac{1}{K_w} \quad (17)$$

for the A-2 mechanism. Equations (17) and (7) are identicals and lead to similar results. As the linear dependence of $(\log k_{obs} - pK_w)$ on $\log C_w$ is very nicely represented, the proposed assumption expressed as equation (6), or (16), seems justified.

If Y is a water molecule and if $C_{SH^+} \ll C_S$, then in aqueous solutions the rate-determining reaction will show first-order kinetic as will the overall reaction at constant acidity, the rate constant k_{obs} will satisfy the equation,

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k'_1}{K_{SH^+}} \frac{C_{H^+}}{C_w^{h-1}} \frac{f_{H^+}}{f_w^{h-1}} \frac{f_s}{f^*} \quad (18)$$

$$\text{or, } k_{obs} = \frac{a'_1 k'_1}{K_{SH^+}} \frac{C_{H^+}}{C_w^{h-1}} \frac{1}{K_w} \quad (19)$$

or, taking logarithms,

$$\log k_{obs} - pK_w = \log C_{H^+} - (h-1) \log C_w + \text{constant.} \quad (20)$$

This equation shows a linear dependence of $(\log k_{obs} - pK_w)$ on $\log C_w$, a relation which was predicted empirically (equation 1). In this case the slope is equal to $(h-1)$ and not to $-h$ as given by the previous cases.

Both of the foregoing A-1 and A-2 mechanisms presuppose a rapid equilibrium between the hydrated reactant S and its hydrated conjugate acid SH^+ . For the particular case of catalysis by a strong acid, evidence for such an equilibrium is afforded by an increase in the reaction rate when D_2O is substituted for H_2O as the reaction medium⁶.

3—A further mechanistic possibility which is relevant to the present discussion is that in which protonation of the hydrated substrate molecule is the rate-determining step in the reaction

The rate equation will have the form :

$$\text{Rate} = -\frac{dC_S}{dt} = k C_S C_{H^+} \frac{f_s f_{H^+}}{f^*} \quad (21)$$

where k is the rate constant for the protonation step. The value of k would of course be different for catalysis by some other acid than the solvated proton. The observed rate constant k_{obs} is given by⁴

$$k_{obs} = -\frac{1}{C_S} \frac{dC_S}{dt} = k C_{H^+} \frac{f_s f_{H^+}}{f^*} \quad (23)$$

taking logarithms,

$$\log k_{obs} - pK_w = \log C_{H^+} + \text{constant} \quad (24)$$

For a fixed acid concentration, $\log k_{obs}$ varies only and directly with pK_w . The proposed designation A- S_{E_2} suggests that this is a typical electrophilic substitution reaction. The difference in the hydration number, h , is equal, in this case, to zero. This mechanism, however, differs from others by being independent on $\log C_w$.

II Base-catalysed reactions

It is evident²⁹ that the theory of Bascombe and Bell^{27,28} is applicable to concentrated alkaline solutions and leads to the conclusion that three moles of water are associated with each mole of hydroxide ion, which may be formulated as $OH(H_2O)_3^-$. However, following the approach developed by Bell and Bascombe^{27,28}, it is profitable to consider the change in solvation for the ionisation in aqueous basic solutions of a weak uncharged acid. This may be represented by the equilibrium,

in which p' , q' and r' are the hydration numbers of HA , OH^- , and A^- respectively and $h' = (p' + q' - r')$ is the difference in hydration numbers on ionisation. Edward and Wang²⁵ take account of the fact that the hydroxide ion, because of its small size and localized charge, is almost certainly more heavily hydrated than the usual organic conjugate base A^- with a charge dispersed by resonance.

Taking into consideration the hydration of the hydroxide ion, the main types of base-catalysed reactions^{24,33} in aqueous-organic solvents may be discussed from the author's point of view as follows : 1-The hydrated substrate SH is in rapid pre-equilibrium with its hydrated conjugate base S^- which is then converted to the products of the reaction in a unimolecular rate-determining step,

In the following treatment only cases $C_S \ll C_{SH}$ will be considered, so that C_{SH} will also represent the total concentration of the substrate. The rate expression is given by

$$-\frac{dC_{SH}}{dt} = k_1 C_S \frac{f_s^-}{f^*} \quad (26)$$

where f^* is the activity coefficient of the transition state. The experimental rate constant, k_{obs} , is given by the equation,

$$k_{obs} = - \frac{1}{C_{SH}} \frac{dC_{SH}}{dt} = k_1 \frac{C_{S^-}}{C_{SH}} \frac{f_{S^-}}{f^*} \quad (27)$$

$$k_{obs} = k_1 K_{SH} \frac{C_{OH^-}}{C_w^{h'+1}} \frac{f_{SH} f_{OH^-}}{f^* f_w^{h'+1}} \quad (28)$$

If the assumption, made in the acid-catalysed reactions, also holds in this case, then

$$\frac{f_{SH} f_{OH^-}}{f^* f_w^{h'+1}} = \frac{b_1}{K_w} \quad (29)$$

where b_1 is a constant and

$$\log k_{obs} - pK_w = \log C_{OH^-} - (h'+1) \log C_w + \text{constant} \quad (30)$$

2—The hydrated substrate SH is in rapid pre-equilibrium with its hydrated conjugate base S^- , as in mechanism 1, but S^- is subsequently converted to the products in a bimolecular rate-determining interaction with another reactant Y,

The rate is given by the equation

$$- \frac{dC_{SH}}{dt} = k_2 C_{S^-} C_Y \frac{f_{S^-} f_Y}{f^*} \quad (31)$$

where k_2 is the rate constant for the slow step and f^* is the activity coefficient of the transition state for that step. The experimental rate constant, k_{obs} , is given by

$$k_{obs} = - \frac{1}{C_{SH} C_Y} \frac{dC_{SH}}{dt} = k_2 K_{SH} \frac{C_{OH^-}}{C_w^{h'+1}} \frac{f_{SH} f_Y f_{OH^-}}{f^* f_w^{h'+1}} \quad (32)$$

Similar treatment to that considered in the previous cases, one obtains

$$\frac{f_{SH} f_Y f_{OH^-}}{f^* f_w^{h'+1}} = \frac{b_2}{K_w} \quad (33)$$

and $\log k_{obs} - pK_w = \log C_{OH^-} - (h'+1) \log C_w + \text{constant} \quad (34)$

Both cases (1) and (2) show a similar linear dependence of $(\log k_{obs} - pK_w)$ on $\log C_w$ at a fixed base concentration except for the values of the constants.

A case of special importance occurs when Y is a water molecule, and the reaction is pseudo-first order. Inserting H_2O instead of Y yields,

$$k_{obs} = - \frac{1}{C_{SH}} \frac{dC_{SH}}{dt} = k_1' K_{SH} \frac{C_{OH^-}}{C_w^{h'}} \frac{f_{OH^-} f_{SH}}{f_w^{h'} f^*}, \quad (35)$$

for the experimental rate constant. It follows that,

$$\log k_{obs} - pK_w = \log C_{OH^-} - h' \log C_w + \text{constant}, \quad (36)$$

$(\log k_{obs} - pK_w)$ of a reaction which proceeds by bimolecular interaction of S^- with a water molecule should be linearly dependent on $\log C_w$ with a slope equal to, $-h'$, the difference in hydration numbers on passing from the reactants to the transition state. 3—An alternative mechanism for base catalysis is that in which the abstraction of a proton from the hydrated reacting substrate is the slow rate-determining step

The rate expression in this case will be

$$- \frac{dC_{SH}}{dt} = k C_{SH} C_{OH^-} \frac{f_{SH} f_{OH^-}}{f^*} \quad (37)$$

The observed rate constant, k_{obs} , is given by

$$k_{obs} = - \frac{1}{C_{SH}} \frac{dC_{SH}}{dt} = k C_{OH^-} \frac{f_{SH} f_{OH^-}}{f^*} = \frac{b k C_{OH^-}}{K_w} \quad (38)$$

taking logarithms,

$$\log k_{obs} - pK_w = \log C_{OH^-} + \text{constant} \quad (39)$$

This equation is identical with equation (24) for A-S₂ mechanism showing the linear dependence of $\log k_{obs}$ on the pK_w for this type of both acid- and base-catalysed reactions. The observed rate constant will therefore behave in the same way in the two cases.

4—A nucleophilic attack on the hydrated substrate by hydrated OH^- ion in the rate determining step,

the transition state in this case is rather similar to that of proton abstraction by OH^- ion (mechanism 3). the difference being only in the point of attack. The rate expression has consequently the same form as equation (39) and can be derived in the same way.

5-Rapid reversible hydroxide additions precede the rate determining step,

followed by (a) $SOH(H_2O)_r^- \rightarrow \text{products}$, (slow)

(b) $SOH(H_2O)_r^- + Y \rightarrow \text{products}$, (slow)

or (c) $SOH(H_2O)_r^- + H_2O \rightarrow \text{products}$, (slow)

Mechanisms of this type are prevalent in base-catalysed reactions in which carbonyl groups are involved, e.g., amide and ester hydrolysis. Consideration of the previous argument leads to the following expressions for the observed rate constants

Mechanism (5a), unimolecular breakdown of hydrated SOH^- , giving

$$k_{obs} = -\frac{1}{C_s} \frac{dC_s}{dt} = kK \frac{C_{OH^-}}{C_w^{h'}} \frac{f_{OH^-} f_s}{f_w^{h'} f^{*1}}$$

$$= \text{const.} \frac{C_{OH^-}}{C_w^{h'}} \frac{1}{K_w} \quad (41)$$

$$\text{or } \log k_{obs} - pK_w = \log C_{OH^-} - h' \log C_w + \text{constant} \quad (42)$$

Mechanism (5b), bimolecular reaction of hydrated SOH^- with a second reactant Y, giving

$$k_{obs} = -\frac{1}{C_s C_Y} \frac{dC_s}{dt} = kK \frac{C_{OH^-}}{C_w^{h'}} \frac{f_{OH^-} f_s f_Y}{f_w^{h'} f^{*1}}$$

$$= \text{const.} \frac{C_{OH^-}}{C_w^{h'}} \frac{1}{K_w}, \quad (43)$$

$$\text{or } \log k_{obs} - pK_w = \log C_{OH^-} - h' \log C_w + \text{constant} \quad (44)$$

Mechanism (5c), a special case where $Y=H_2O$, giving

$$k_{obs} = -\frac{1}{C_s} \frac{dC_s}{dt} = kK \frac{C_{OH^-}}{C_w^{h-1}} \frac{f_{OH^-} f_s}{f_w^{h-1} f^{*1}}$$

$$= \text{const.} \frac{C_{OH^-}}{C_w^{h-1}} \frac{1}{K_w}, \quad (45)$$

$$\text{or } \log k_{obs} - pK_w = \log C_{OH^-} - (h-1) \log C_w + \text{constant.} \quad (46)$$

where k is the rate constant of the slow step and K is the pseudo-equilibrium constant of equation (40).

Results and Discussion

1 Water-dioxane system

A comparative discussion can now be made for the acid- and base-catalysed reactions, in water-dioxane mixtures, in terms of the dependence of the rate function L ($L = \log k_{obs} - pK_w$) on $\log C_w$. The water-dioxane system has often been useful in studies of the effect of solvent on acidic and basic dissociation, partly because it covers such a wide range of dielectric constant. Water ionisation constant values for the different water-dioxane mixtures over the temperature range 25-50° were adopted from Harned and Fainon data²⁸ by interpolation (up to about 81 wt.% of dioxane) from sufficiently large scale plots. The rate expressions of acid-catalysed reactions, may be divided into three groups

1-The first comprise the A-1 and A-2 mechanisms ($C_{SH^+} \ll C_s$) where the rate of reaction will thus follow the equation (9). An example of a reaction following the A-1 mechanism is the acid-catalysed rearrangement of phenylpropenyl- and ethynylpropenyl-carbinol⁸ over the entire range of medium composition. The data are given in Table 1. Least square method was generally used to calculate the slopes of all the straight lines and these are given in Table 7. The acid hydrolysis of benzylacetate¹⁹ is an example of an A-2 mechanism. The data are shown in Fig. 1 and Tables 2 and 7. The hydrolysis of tert.butylacetate in presence of 0.05N HCl in several dioxane-water mixtures (0-90% dioxane by weight) was examined²⁰. The reaction mechanism changes from A_{AL}^1 , which predominates in water, to A_{AC}^2 which prevails in dioxane-rich solvents. However, very good straight lines were obtained and the data are given in Tables 3 and 7.

2-The special case of the A-2 mechanism ($Y=H_2O$) represents the second group where the rate of reaction can be expected to follow the equation (20). Examples are given (Tables 4 and 5) for the acid-hydrolysis of acetamide¹⁷ and methyl-toluene-p-sulphinat¹⁶. Very good straight lines were obtained (Fig. 1) where the slopes represent the $-(h-1)$ values (Table 7).

TABLE-1 REARRANGEMENTS OF (I) PHENYLPROPENYL- (IN 0.1M HCl) AND (II) ETHYNYLPROPENYL-CARBINOL⁸ (IN 1M HCl) IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES AT 30°.

Vol. % log C _w pK _w	20 1.648 14.48	40 1.523 15.36	60 1.347 16.79	70 1.222 17.81	80 1.046 19.32
(I) 21+L	6.847	5.515	3.532	2.280	0.519
(II) 21+L	4.538	3.124	1.278	0.199	-

TABLE—2 ACID HYDROLYSIS OF BENZYLACETATE IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES¹⁹ (IN 0.05M HCl)

Wt.%	15.45	30.60	40.71	50.46	60.48	70.21	80.33
log C _w	1.675	1.594	1.528	1.452	1.355	1.235	1.054
25°							
pK _w	14.46	15.04	15.52	16.07	16.87	17.88	19.44
25+L	6.875	6.210	5.681	5.047	4.135	3.012	—
30°							
pK _w	14.30	14.86	15.35	15.96	16.75	17.73	19.28
25+L	7.257	6.640	6.091	5.392	4.498	3.407	1.788
35°							
pK _w	14.15	14.73	15.22	15.81	16.61	17.60	19.15
25+L	7.632	6.972	6.421	5.740	4.820	3.724	2.096
40°							
pK _w	14.00	14.59	15.08	15.66	16.48	17.46	19.02
25+L	7.929	7.273	6.715	6.038	5.126	4.080	2.436
45°							
pK _w	13.84	14.46	14.94	15.52	16.32	17.33	18.88
25+L	8.269	7.573	7.032	6.380	5.479	4.363	2.750

TABLE—3 ACID HYDROLYSIS OF TERT.-BUTYLACETATE IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES²⁰ (IN 0.05M HCl)

Wt.%	00.00	15.64	31.57	50.06	69.47	79.47
log C _w	1.745	1.671	1.580	1.443	1.230	1.057
30°						
pK _w	13.83	14.31	14.90	15.93	17.64	19.15
24+L	6.917	6.315	5.360	4.047	1.994	0.316
40°						
pK _w	13.54	14.00	14.63	15.63	17.38	18.89
24+L	7.906	7.240	6.359	5.039	2.819	1.038
50°						
pK _w	13.26	13.73	14.37	15.34	17.12	18.62
24+L	8.665	7.968	7.102	5.797	3.531	1.896

TABLE—4 ACID HYDROLYSIS OF ACETAMIDE IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES¹⁷ (IN 0.1 M HCl)

Wt.%	0	15	30	40	60	75
log C _w	1.745	1.676	1.597	1.497	1.360	1.158
35°						
pK _w	13.68	14.13	14.71	15.44	16.57	18.32
20+L	5.335	4.819	4.206	3.461	2.362	0.744
40°						
pK _w	13.54	13.98	14.59	15.29	16.43	18.20
20+L	5.687	5.179	4.557	3.817	2.720	1.094
50°						
pK _w	13.26	13.72	14.30	15.03	16.14	17.92
20+L	6.363	5.846	5.232	4.482	3.409	1.785

TABLE—5 ACID HYDROLYSIS METHYLTOLUENE-*p*-SULPHINATE¹⁶ IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES (IN 0.2 M HClO₄) AT 25.2°

Vol.%	40	60	65	70	75	80
log C _w	1.523	1.347	1.289	1.222	1.143	1.046
pK _w	15.53	16.90	17.40	17.96	18.69	19.47
26+L	5.166	3.628	3.101	2.458	1.683	0.925

3-The last group represents the mechanism 3 where the rate of reaction will follow the equation (24). Unfortunately, no experimental data for a reaction known to proceed by mechanism 3 are available at present.

The rate expressions of base-catalysed reactions may also be divided into four groups.

1-The first comprises the mechanisms 1 and 2 where the rate of the reaction will follow the equation (30).

2-The second group comprises the special case of mechanism 2 (Y=H₂O), and mechanisms 5a and 5b, the rate of reaction can be expected to follow the equation (36).

3-The third group comprises mechanisms 3 and 4 where the rate of reaction can be expected to follow the equation (39).

Here again it is to be regretted that no experimental rate data regarding these mechanisms are available at present.

4-The last group is the mechanism 5c where the rate of reaction can be expected to follow the equation (46). An example is the alkaline hydrolysis of acetamide¹⁸ (Tables 6 and 7). Very good straight lines are also obtained (Fig. 1).

TABLE—6 ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF ACETAMIDE IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES¹⁸ (IN 0.1M NaOH)

Wt.%	0	10	20	30	40	50
log C _w	1.745	1.700	1.651	1.597	1.531	1.453
25°						
pK _w	14.00	14.29	14.62	15.02	15.49	16.04
18+L	3.137	2.740	2.305	1.807	1.245	0.613
35°						
pK _w	13.68	13.97	14.31	14.71	15.18	15.77
18+L	3.812	3.458	3.027	2.540	1.981	1.324
40°						
pK _w	13.54	13.82	14.16	14.59	15.04	15.63
18+L	4.135	3.792	3.363	2.855	2.339	1.672
50°						
pK _w	13.26	13.55	13.89	14.30	14.77	15.34
18+L	4.786	4.422	4.011	3.526	2.981	2.363

TABLE—7 THE SLOPES OF THE STRAIGHT LINES OBTAINED

Temp. °C	25	30	35	40	45	50
Ref. 8 (I)	-	9.86	-	-	-	-
Ref. 8 (II)	-	10.16	-	-	-	-
Ref. 19	8.78	8.90	8.99	8.90	8.93	-
Ref. 20	-	9.66	-	10.02	-	9.92
Ref. 17	-	-	7.82	7.83	-	7.79
Ref. 16	9.01*	-	-	-	-	-
Ref. 18	8.69	-	9.59	8.50	-	8.37

*25.2°

Consequently, it seems likely that the slope of the straight line, obtained by plotting of the rate function L against log C_w, enables, in principle, a distinction to be made between these different groups of either acid- or base-catalysed reactions.

It would be helpful to make further studies²⁴ to ascertain the generality of the author's hypothesis. In this case, there is every reason to believe that this hypothesis will be highly useful.

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